

EXPRESSIVE,EFFICIENT,AND REVOCABLE DATA ACCESS CONTROL FOR MULTI-AUTHORITY CLOUD STORAGE

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Abstract:

Data access control is an effective way to ensure the data security in the cloud. Due to data outsourcing and untrusted cloud servers, the data access control becomes a challenging issue in cloud storage systems. Cipher text-Policy Attribute-based Encryption (CP-ABE) is regarded as one of the most suitable technologies for data access control in cloud storage, because it gives data owners more direct control on access policies. However, it is difficult to directly apply existing CP-ABE schemes to data access control for cloud storage systems because of the attribute revocation problem. In this paper, we design an expressive, efficient and revocable data access control scheme for multi-authority cloud storage systems, where there are multiple authorities co-exist and each authority is able to issue attributes independently. Specifically, we propose a revocable multi-authority CP-ABE scheme, and apply it as the underlying techniques to design the data access control scheme. Our attribute revocation method can efficiently achieve both forward security and backward security. The analysis and simulation results show that our proposed data access control scheme is secure in the random oracle model and is more efficient than previous works.

Key words - Access control, multi-authority, CP-ABE, attribute revocation, cloud storage

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 OVERVIEW

Cloud storage is a vital service of cloud computing, which offers services for data owners to host their data in the cloud. This new model of data hosting and data access services introduces a great challenge to data access control. Because the cloud server cannot be fully trusted by data owners, they can no longer

depend on servers to do access control. Cipher text-Policy Attribute-based Encryption (CPABE) is regarded as one of the most suitable technologies for data access control in cloud storage systems, because it gives the data owner more direct control on access policies. In CP-ABE scheme, there is an authority that is responsible for attribute management and key distribution. The authority can be the registration office in a university, the human resource department in a company, etc. The data owner defines the access policies and encrypts data according to the policies. Each user will be issued a secret key reflecting its attributes. A user can decrypt the data only when its attributes satisfy the access policies. There are two types of CP-ABE systems: single-authority CP-ABE where all attributes are managed by a single authority, and multi-authority CP-ABE where attributes are from different domains and managed by different authorities. Multi-authority CP-ABE is more appropriate for data access control of cloud storage systems, as users may hold attributes issued by multiple authorities and data owners may also share the data using access policy defined over attributes from different authorities. For example, in an E-health system, data owners may share the data using the access policy “Doctor AND Researcher”, where the attribute “Doctor” is issued by a medical organization and the attribute “Researcher” is issued by the administrators of a clinical trial. However, it is difficult to directly apply these multi-authority CP-ABE schemes to multi authority cloud storage systems because of the attribute revocation problem.

1.1.1 REVOCABLE MULTI AUTHORITY CIPHER TEXT –POLICY ATTRIBUTE BASED ENCRYPTION (CP-ABE) SCHEME FOR CLOUD STORAGE

In a cloud computing the data security is achieved by data access control scheme. Cipher text-policy attribute-based encryption (CP-ABE) is considered as one of the most suitable scheme for data access control on access policies. However CP-ABE schemes to data access control for cloud storage system are difficult because of the attribute revocation problem. So this paper produce serve on efficient and revocable data access control scheme for multi authority cloud storage system where there are multiple authorities co-operate and each authority is able to issue attribute independently

Cloud computing is one of the emerging technologies. The cloud computing contains huge open distributed system. It is important to protect the data and privacy of the users. Access control may also identify users attempting to access a system unauthorized. It is a mechanism which is very much important for protection in computer security. The cloud storage is an important service of cloud computing. The cloud storage offers services for data owners to host there data in to the cloud. The data access control becomes a challenging issue in cloud storage systems because of data out source in untrusted cloud service. There for cloud storage is a model or model of data storage where the digital data is stored in logical pool.

One of the most suitable technologies for data access control in cloud storage systems is cipher text policy attribute based encryption (CP-ABE). This scheme provides the data owner more direct control on access policies. The data owner in CPABE scheme defines the access policies and encrypts the data according to the policies.

There are two types of CPABE systems. They are single authority CPABE and multi authority CP-ABE in a single authority CPABE scheme where all attributes are managed by a single authority. In a multi authority CPABE scheme where attributes are from different domains and managed by different authorities.

This paper surveys a revocable multi authority CPABE scheme to solve the attribute revocation problem in the system. This method is an efficient and secure revocation method. Attribute revocation method can efficiently achieve both forward security and backward security. An attribute revocation method is efficient in the sense that it incurs less communication cost and computation cost, secure in the sense that it can achieve both backward security and forward security. In backward security scheme the revoked user can't decrypt any new cipher text that requires the revoked attribute to decrypt. In forward security the newly joined user can also decrypt the previously published cipher text if it has sufficient attributes.

This survey explains a revocable multi authority CPABE scheme that can support efficient attribute revocation. Then the effective data access control scheme for multi authority cloud storage system is proposed. The revocable multi authority CPABE is an efficient technique, which can be applied in any remote storage system and online social network etc....

1.1.2 PRIVACY AND SECURE REVOCABLE DATA ACCESS CONTROL IN MULTI-AUTHORITY CLOUD STORAGE

Cloud users use "Cloud storage" service to host their data in the cloud. Access control service provided by cloud is used for giving protection against unauthorized access to data. Cipher text-Policy Attribute-Based Encryption (CP-ABE) is mostly considered for data access control in cloud storage.

Cloud Computing servers provide a promising platform for storage of data. Sharing of personal medical records is an emerging patient-centric model of health information exchange, which is often outsourced to store at third party, such as cloud providers. Attribute based encryption (ABE) techniques to encrypt each patient's medical record file. The technique describes a new mechanism which enables secure storage and controlled sharing of patient's health data.

Techniques explore Key Policy Attribute Based Encryption (KPABE) and Multi Authority Attribute Based Encryption to enforce patient access control policy such that all the users of system can

download the data ,but only authorize user can view the medical records. framework of secure sharing of individual medical records in cloud computing, utilize various forms of ABE to encrypt the medical record files, so that patients can allow access not only by individual users, but also various users from public domains with different professional roles, qualifications and affiliations[8].Advantages of technique are:

1.Multiple security domains.2.Reduce the key management complexity for owners and users.3.A high degree of patient privacy is guaranteed by exploiting multi-authority ABE framework.

Limitations of technique are: 1.The framework addresses the unique challenges brought by multiple owners and users.2. Storing personal medical records on the cloud server leads to need of Encryption Mechanism.

A revocable multi-authority cipher text policy attribute based encryption (CP-ABE) scheme can support efficient attribute revocation. Then, technique constructed an effective data access control strategy for multi-authority cloud storage systems. The revocable multi-authority cipher text policy attribute based encryption (CP-ABE) is a promising technique, which can be register in any remote storage systems and online social networks (OSN) etc.

1.1.3 STUDY ON REVOCABLE DATA ACCESS CONTROL SCHEME FOR MULTI AUTHORITY CLOUD STORAGE SYSTEMS

Cloud computing multi-tenancy feature, which provides privacy, security and access control challenges, because of sharing of physical resources among untrusted tenants. In order to achieve safe storage, policy based file access control, policy based file assured deletion and policy based renewal of a file stored in a cloud environment, a suitable encryption technique with key management should be applied before outsourcing the data.

Cloud computing is an environment that enables users to remotely store their data. Remote backup system is the advanced concept which reduces the cost for implementing more memory in an organization. It helps enterprises and government agencies reduce their financial overhead of data management. There are three objectives to be main issue Confidentiality, Integrity and availability. To achieve secure data transaction in cloud, suitable cryptography method is used. The cloud computing contains huge open distributed system. It is important to protect the data and privacy of users. Access Control methods ensure that authorized users access the data and the system. Access control is generally a policy or procedure that allows, denies or restricts access to a system. It may, as well, monitor and record all attempts made to access a system.

The Cloud Storage offers services for data owners to host their data into the cloud. Cloud storage is a model of data storage where the digital data is stored in logical pool. One of the most suitable

technologies for data access control in cloud storage systems is Cipher text-Policy Attribute-based Encryption (CP-ABE). This scheme provides the data owner more direct control on access policies. The data owner in CP-ABE scheme defines the access policies and encrypts data according to the policies. There are two types of CP-ABE systems are **SINGLE-AUTHORITY** , **CP-ABE MULTI-AUTHORITY CP-ABE**. **IN SINGLE-AUTHORITY CP-ABE SCHEME**, where all attributes are managed by a single authority. **IN A MULTI-AUTHORITY CP-ABE SCHEME** where attributes are from different domains and managed by different authorities.

An attribute revocation method is efficient in the sense that it incurs less communication cost and computation cost, secure in the sense that it can achieve both backward security and forward security. Data access control system in multi authority cloud storage there are five types of entities in the system. Certificate authority (CA), Attribute authorities (AAs), Data owners (owners), Cloud server(server) Data consumers (users). every attribute is associated with a single AA, but each AA can manage an arbitrary number of attributes. Every AA has full control over the structure and semantics of its attributes.

This paper, surveys a revocable multi authority CP-ABE scheme , to solve the attribute revocation problem in the system. This method is an efficient and secure revocation method. The attribute revocation method can efficiently achieve both forward security and backward security. In backward security scheme the revoked user cannot decrypt any new Cipher text that requires the revoked attribute to decrypt. In Forward security the newly joined user can also decrypt the previously published cipher texts, if it has sufficient attributes.

1.1.4 ATTRIBUTE BASED REVOCABLE DATA ACCESS CONTROL FOR MULTI AUTHORITY CLOUD STORAGE

Cloud Computing is emerging tremendously due to its advantages and the flexible storage services provided by it. Due to this the number of users has reached at the top. Obviously the users will be sharing the sensitive data through the cloud. And the user can't believe the untrusted cloud server. Hence the data access control has become very challenging in cloud storage system. Cloud Computing provides so many services in that the most important service which is provided by it is cloud storage service. The data owners can store the huge amount of data into the cloud server and the data will be accessible flexibly from everywhere. This property of cloud not only provides the benefit but also creates major challenge to data access control.

Data access control scheme is more important hence more works have conducted in this field the important and related works have been discussed here. Cipher text-Policy Attribute Based encryption

(CP-ABE), Single Authority Cipher text-Policy Attribute Based encryption, multi authority cipher text policy attribute based encryption, Attribute revocation

The proposed system overcomes the problem exist in the existing system. We proposed a new algorithm named as Improved Security data Access Control. This algorithm improves the security of the system. The data owner when stores the data into the cloud server he encrypts it and then stores it. This system not only provides forward and backward security but it also provides improved security by providing access control on authorised users. The algorithm proposed by us improves the security by informing about the attack to the data owner. We also provided the data integrity. As the data owner comes to know about the verification in the data stored when he verifies it.

There are five modules. They are, Certificate authority (CA), Attribute authorities (AAs), Data owners, Cloud servers and Data consumers. CA is a global trusted certificate authority in the system. It sets up the system and accepts the registration of all the users and AAs in the system. Every AAs independent attribute authority that is responsible for entitling and revoking user's attributes according to their role or identity in its domain.

Our Data access control scheme is secure where we achieve forward security, backward security, improved security, and data integrity. Forward Security is achieved when any new user is joined . In backward security Each time when the secret key update algorithm runs it provides new secret key to all the authorized users. Improved security when the authorized user tries to access the data for which he is not having the attribute at that time this will come into picture. Data integrity is maintained by data owner. As the number of users in cloud computing increasing security issues are also increasing accordingly. The main security issue can be how to control the unauthorized data access in cloud.

II. SYSTEM ANALYSIS

2.1 EXISTING SYSTEM

This new paradigm of data hosting and data access services introduces a great challenge to data access control. Because the cloud server cannot be fully trusted by data owners, they can no longer rely on servers to do access control. (CP-ABE) is regarded as one of the most suitable technologies for data access control in cloud storage systems, because it gives the data owner more direct control on access policies. In CP-ABE scheme, there is an authority that is responsible for attribute management and key distribution.

2.1.1 DRAWBACKS

- Chase's multi-authority CP-ABE protocol allows the central authority to decrypt all the cipher texts, since it holds the master key of the system.
- Chase's protocol does not supports attribute revocation.

2.2 PROPOSED SYSTEM

we first propose a revocable multi authority CP-ABE scheme, where an efficient and secure revocation method is proposed to solve the attribute revocation problem in the system. Our attribute revocation method is efficient in the sense that it incurs less communication cost and computation cost, and is secure in the sense that it can achieve both backward security (The revoked user cannot decrypt any new cipher text that requires the revoked attribute to decrypt)and forward security (The newly joined user can also decrypt the previously published ciphertexts1, if it has sufficient. attributes). Our scheme does not require the server to be fully trusted, because the key update is enforced by each attribute authority not the server. Even if the server is not semi trusted in some scenarios, our scheme can still guarantee the backward security. Then, we apply our proposed revocable multi-authority CP-ABE scheme as the underlying techniques to construct the expressive and secure data access control scheme for multi-authority cloud storage systems

2.2.2 ADVANTAGES OF PROPOSED SYSTEM

- We modify the framework of the scheme and make it more practical to cloud storage systems, in which data owners are not involved in the key generation.
- We greatly improve the efficiency of the attribute revocation method.
- We also highly improve the expressiveness of our access control scheme, where we remove the limitation that each attribute can only appear at most once in a cipher text.

III. SYSTEM DESIGN AND IMPLEMENTATION MODELS

3.1 IMPLEMENTATION MODULES

In our Expressive, Efficient and Revocable data access for multi authority cloud storage consists of several modules. They are:

1. Certificate Authority
2. Attribute Authority
3. Data consumers
4. Data Owners
5. Cloud Servers

3.1.1 Certificate Authority

The CA is a global trusted certificate authority is a global trusted certificate authority in the system. It sets up the system and accepts the registration of all the users and AAs in the system. For each legal user in the system, the CA assigns a global unique user identity to it and also generates a global public key for this user. However, the CA is not involved in any attribute management and the creation of secret keys that are associated with attributes. For example, the CA can be the Social Security Administration, an independent agency of the United States government. Each user will be issued a Social Security Number (SSN) as its global identity.

3.1.2 Attribute Authority

Every AA is an independent attribute authority that is responsible for entitling and revoking user's attributes according to their role or identity in its domain. In our scheme, every attribute is associated with a single AA, but each AA can manage an arbitrary number of attributes. Every AA has full control over the structure and semantics of its attributes. Each AA is responsible for generating a public attribute key for each attribute it manages and a secret key for each user reflecting his/her attributes.

3.1.3 Data Consumers

Each user has a global identity in the system. A user may be entitled a set of attributes which may come from multiple attribute authorities. The user will receive a secret key associated with its attributes entitled by the corresponding attribute authorities.

3.1.4 Data Owners

Each owner first divides the data into several components according to the logic granularities and encrypts each data component with different content keys by using symmetric encryption techniques. Then, the owner defines the access policies over attributes from multiple attribute authorities and encrypts the content keys under the policies.

3.1.5 Cloud Servers

Then, the owner sends the encrypted data to the cloud server together with the cipher texts. They do not rely on the server to do data access control. But the data control access happens inside the cryptography. That is only when the user's attributes satisfy the access policy defined in the cipher text; the user is able to decrypt the cipher text. Thus, users with different attributes can decrypt different number of content keys and thus obtain different granularities of information from the same data.

3.2 SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig.4.2.1 Overall Architecture

There are five types of entities in the system AS IN Fig 7.1.1 a certificate authority (CA), attribute authorities (AAs), data owners (owners), the cloud server (server) and data consumers (users). The CA is a global trusted certificate authority in the system. It sets up the system and accepts the registration of all the users and AAs in the system. For each legal user in the system, the CA assigns a global unique user identity to it and also generates a global public key for this user. However, the CA is not involved in any attribute management and the creation of secret keys that are associated with attributes. For example, the CA can be the Social Security Administration, an independent agency of the United States government. Each user will be issued a Social Security Number (SSN) as its global identity. Every AA is an independent attribute authority that is responsible for entitling and revoking user's attributes according to their role or identity in its domain. In our scheme, every attribute is associated with a single AA, but each AA can manage an arbitrary number of attributes. Every AA has full control over the structure and semantics of its attributes. Each AA is responsible for generating a public attribute key for each attribute it manages and a secret key. For each user reflecting his/her attributes.

IV. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we propose a revocable multi-authority CP- ABE scheme that can support efficient attribute revocation. Then, we constructed an effective data access control scheme for multi-authority cloud storage systems.

We also proved that our scheme was provable secure in the random oracle model. The revocable multi-authority CP- ABE is a promising technique, which can be applied in any remote storage systems and online social networks etc. Cloud storage is an important service of cloud computing which offers services for data owners to host their data in the cloud. This new paradigm of data hosting and data access services introduces a great challenges to data access control .we propose a revocable multi authority CP- ABE scheme and apply it as the underlying techniques to design the data access control scheme.

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